

Analysis of Financial Literacy Levels in Generations Baby Boomers, X, Y, and Z Small Traders

Yani Riyani

Pontianak State Polytechnic, Pontianak, Indonesia
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-7289-1583>

Kartawati Mardiah

Pontianak State Polytechnic, Pontianak, Indonesia
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-2202-1606>

Susan Andriana

Pontianak State Polytechnic, Pontianak, Indonesia
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-0024-275X>

Linda Suherma

Pontianak State Polytechnic, Pontianak, Indonesia
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0000-3651-3316>

Agus Widodo

Pontianak State Polytechnic, Pontianak, Indonesia
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0586-4225>

Endri Endri*

Universitas Mercu Buana, Jakarta, Indonesia.
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8613-6149>

*Corresponding author: Email: endri@mercubuana.ac.id

Abstract

Background: Financial Literacy (FL) is crucial for investors to enhance their understanding and utilise economic data to make informed decisions about financial planning, wealth accumulation, retirement, and debt management.

Objective: This study aims to determine the literacy level of small traders classified by birth generation, whether the level of FL for each generation is different, and whether the level of literacy affects their ability to manage finances

Methodology: This research is descriptive and associative. Data were collected through questionnaire copies, and of the 48 distributed questionnaires, 41 were deemed eligible for processing. The stages of data processing carried out included calculating the highest and lowest scores, the average, and standard deviation for each generation, conducting a difference test, and performing a linear regression analysis.

Results. This study found that the variance in financial literacy (FL) levels across each generation (baby boomers, X, Y, and Z) was the same. Second, the level of FL between baby boomers and Generation X, between baby boomers and Generation Y, between baby boomers and Generation Z, between Generation X and Y, and between Generation X and Z is the same, but different between Generations Y and Z when viewed in terms of means. Third, the level of financial management ability of each generation (baby boomers, X, Y and Z) is the same in terms of variance and means. Fourth, the level of FL of each generation influences their ability to manage their finances. Fifth, the magnitude of the influence of the level of FL on the ability to manage finances is 14%, with the remaining 86% of the ability to manage finances influenced by factors other than the level of FL.

Conclusion: The FL levels of each generation (baby boomers, X, Y, and Z) exhibit the same variance, indicating no difference in risk between them.

Unique contribution: This research has made a significant contribution to the literature on the literacy level of small traders, specifically in relation to their birth generation, in the areas of financial management and investment.

Key Recommendation: It is recommended that the governments plan and implement training programs aimed at developing individual investors' financial literacy and competency.

Keywords: Financial Literacy; Small Traders; Generation; Indonesia

Introduction

Financial Literacy (FL) is a new concept in Indonesia, although world history shows that FL has existed since 1787. FL is the ability to read, analyze, manage, and discuss a person's financial situation, which impacts well-being (Huston, 2010). FL is a basic need for people as a provision for getting a better life (Susanto et al., 2025). Someone with a high level of FL can avoid financial difficulties. Financial difficulties occur not only because of low income but also because the level of FL they have is low, so someone cannot plan and manage finances, has errors in managing loan funds, and does not have savings for the future.

The results of the Otoritas Jasa Keuangan (OJK) survey as a financial services institution on literacy found that Indonesia's FL index score from 2013 to 2022, although constantly increasing, remained in the low category with results in 2013 = 21.8%, in 2016 = 29.7%, in 2019 = 38.03% while in 2022 it was 49.68%. Likewise, the world FL survey results conducted in several countries found a low literacy level in high-income countries, very low for upper-middle-income countries, and lower-middle income (Karakurum-Ozdemir et al., 2019). Many factors influence the level of

FL. Gutter et al. (2008) found that knowledge, attitudes, and financial behavior influence the level of FL, while Mancebón et al. (2019) stated that these factors influence the level of FL education.

Objectives of the study

This study has four objectives: first, to determine the level of financial literacy in each generation—Baby Boomers, X, Y, and Z. Second, to assess whether the financial literacy levels of the Baby Boomer, X, Y, and Z generations differ significantly. Third, examine whether each generation—Baby Boomers, X, Y, and Z—has varying financial management abilities. Fourth, the influence of financial literacy on each generation—Baby Boomers, X, Y, and Z—on their ability to manage finances will be analysed.

This research has both practical and theoretical contributions. The local government contributes to creating policies or programs to improve FL for traditional market traders and their welfare. Theoretically, it is used as study material to enrich knowledge and references regarding FL related to the birth generation.

Literature Review

Financial Literacy (FL)

FL is a person's cognitive and educational abilities that influence financial behaviour (Yanti et al., 2024). Andarsari and Ningtyas (2019) define FL as an individual's knowledge of managing finances. Huston (2010) defines it as a person's ability to analyse financial conditions that impact financial behaviour and decision-making. Wijaya et al. (2024) stated that FL is knowledge and beliefs that influence attitudes and behavior in financial management. FL demonstrates an individual's understanding of personal financial management and well-being (Cwynar, 2020; Endri et al., 2019).

Aspects of Financial Literacy

Aspects of financial management consist of three categories: first, general-personal finance, namely knowledge about personal finance; second, saving and borrowing, namely insight related to savings and loans; and third, insurance, namely insight into the basics of accounting and insurance products (Widyastuti et al., 2022).

Indicators of Financial Literacy

Australian Securities and Investment Commission states that indicators of FL consist of:

1. Knowledge of the value of goods and life priorities.
2. Budget, saving, and how to manage money.
3. Managing loans/credit.
4. The need for insurance and risk protection.
5. Investment insight
6. Future planning (retirement).
7. Using money for shopping and product choices.
8. Recognizing conflicts over priority scales.

Generation

According to ~~Abramson~~ Abrahamson (2016), people born into different generations will have different attitudes and behaviors. This is because their external environment influences their attitudes, behaviors, and actions.

Furthermore, Abramson (2016) divides the generations into 4, namely:

1. Baby Boomers Generation

The generation born between 1946 and 1964 is characterized by high commitment, independence, and competitiveness.

2. Generation X

This generation was born between 1965 and 1980. They lived in a time of rapid technological development, but were not as sophisticated as they are today. Generation X grew up in the digital world but still experienced the era of non-digital environments and understood both. Generation X has the characteristics of being intelligent, logical, and reasonable decision-makers.

1. Generation Y or Millennials

This generation was born between 1980 and 1996. This millennial generation prefers to spend their money on snacks rather than investment savings, and they are proficient in the digital world. Generation Y has the characteristics of being confident, curious, and questioning authority (Endri et al., 2020).

2. Generation Z

Generation Z was born between 1997 and 2009. It is a relatively young generation that has never experienced life without technology. Generation Z is ambitious, digital native, and self-confident.

Previous Studies

Potrich et al. (2024) found that Generation Z exhibited lower levels of FL than Generation Y and X and were more similar to Baby Boomers. Pokharel and Maharjan (2024) revealed that Generation Z and Millennials differ in FL, ethics, and attitudes that shape their financial behavior. Generation Z has good self-control in saving activities (Xie et al., 2023). Patricia et al. (2023) proved that the level of FL of Generation Z is influenced by communication patterns within the family. Rahmadani et al. (2023) confirmed that FL has a positive impact on better financial management behavior in Generation Z. Onyango (2021) revealed that financial knowledge, attitudes, and financial locus of control have a positive impact on the personal financial decisions of Generation X and Y. Mawad et al. (2022) proved that Generation X and Z have good financial literacy in improving personal financial performance and behavior.

Based on the above review, the hypotheses are formulated as follows:

H1: There is a difference in the level of financial literacy across generations.

H2: There is a difference in financial management abilities across generations.

H3: Each generation's financial literacy level influences their ability to manage finances.

Methodology

The research design employed is an associative study involving data collection, processing, and analysis to determine whether there are differences and associations between two or more variables. These associations will then be interpreted to address the research hypotheses.

The population in this study consists of 48 traders at the Public Market in Pontianak. The sampling technique used is a census, in which every member of the population is studied without selecting specific samples. The census method was chosen because the population is relatively small, allowing the entire population to be used as the sample. Therefore, the total sample size consists of 48 traders.

The data collection method involves distributing questionnaires to the 48 respondents. Out of the 48 questionnaires returned, 41 (85%) were deemed valid for analysis, while 7 (15%) were considered unusable. The 41 valid responses were then classified based on generation:

- Baby Boomers: 6 traders
- Generation X: 14 traders
- Generation Y: 13 traders
- Generation Z: 8 traders

This study utilises two dependent and independent variables, each categorised by generation.

- The dependent variable (Y) is financial management ability.
- The independent variable (X) is financial literacy level.

Both variables are measured using a five-point Likert scale. Each question representing the variables is tested for validity and reliability. A variable is considered valid if its correlation value exceeds 0.3, and reliable if Cronbach's alpha coefficient is greater than 0.6.

With the assistance of SPSS software, the following analytical methods are used to address the research problem:

1. The financial literacy level and financial management ability variables were validated and reliability tested. The validity test was conducted using correlation analysis, while the reliability test was performed using Cronbach's alpha statistical test.
2. Calculate the highest score, lowest score, mean, and standard deviation for each generation.
3. Comparative tests of literacy levels and financial management skills across generations used independent sample tests, which included Levene's test for equality of variances and t-tests for equality of means.
4. Simple linear regression analysis examines the influence of financial literacy levels on the financial management abilities of public market traders.

Results

The sample used in this study was 41 small traders divided into four generations: the baby boomer generation, with six traders; Generation X, with 14 traders; Generation Y, with 13 traders; and Generation Z, with eight traders. The results of the descriptive analysis are as follows:

1. Financial Literacy Level

To determine each generation's financial literacy level using six questions with a 5-point Likert scale

- a. With knowledge about the benefits and how to manage finances, the baby boomer generation obtained a score range from 4 to 5, with an average of 4.17 and a standard deviation of 0.408. In Generation X, the score range was from 4 to 5, and the average was 4.14, with a standard deviation of 0.363. In Generation Y, the range was 4 to 5, and the average was 4.46, with a standard deviation of 0.519. In Generation Z, the score range was 4 to 5, and the average was 4.13, with a standard deviation of 0.354.
- b. Knowledge of the benefits and how to make a budget plan; in the baby boomer generation, the range of values is from 3 to 5, with a mean of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 0.632. In Generation X, the range of values is from 3 to 5, and the mean is 4.07, with a standard deviation of 0.475. In Generation Y, the range of values is from 3 to 5, with a mean of 4.23 and a standard deviation of 0.599. In Generation Z, the range of values is from 1 to 4, and the mean is 3.63, with a standard deviation of 1.061.
- c. Knowledge of the benefits of saving. In the baby boomer generation, the score range is 4 to 5, with a mean of 4.50 and a standard deviation of 0.548. In Generation X, the score range is 4 to 5, and the mean is 4.50, with a standard deviation of 0.519. In Generation Y, the score range is 4 to 5, and the mean is 4.54, with a standard deviation of 0.519. In Generation Z, the score range is 2 to 5, and the mean is 4.13, with a standard deviation of 0.991.
- d. Knowledge of aspects to consider when taking out a loan or credit. In the baby boomer generation, the range of values is from 2 to 5, with an average of 3.50 and a standard deviation of 1.092. In Generation X, the range of values is from 2 to 5, and the average is 3.64, with a standard deviation of 1.216. In Generation Y, the range of values is from 2 to 5, with an average of 4.00 with a standard deviation of 1.080. In Generation Z, the range of values is from 2 to 4, and the average is 3.75, with a standard deviation of 0.707.
- e. Knowledge of the benefits of investing income to obtain future benefits. In the baby boomer generation, the range of values is 4 to 5, with an average of 4.17 and a standard deviation of 0.408. In Generation X, the range of values is 4 to 5, and the average is 4.50, with a standard deviation of 0.519. In Generation Y, the range of values is 2 to 5, and the average is 4.23, with a standard deviation of 0.832. In Generation Z, the range of values is 4 to 5, and the average is 4.13, with a standard deviation of 0.354.
- f. Participation in training on small and medium enterprises. In the baby boomer generation, the lowest value is 1, and the highest is 4, with an average of 3.00 and a standard deviation of 1.265. In Generation X, the lowest value is 1, the highest value is 4, and the average is 3.07, with a standard deviation of 1.207. In Generation Y, the lowest value is 2, the highest value is 5, and the average is 3.15, with a standard deviation of 1.144. In Generation Z,

the lowest value is 2, the highest value is 4, and the average is 2.63, with a standard deviation of 0.916.

2. Level of Financial Management Ability.

To find out the level of financial management ability in each generation using six questions with a 5-point Likert scale, namely:

- a. Recording business income and expenses. In the baby boomer generation, the range of values is from 3 to 5, with a mean of 4.33 and a standard deviation of 0.816. In Generation X, the range of values is from 4 to 5, and the mean is 4.43, with a standard deviation of 0.514. In Generation Y, the range of values is from 2 to 5, and the mean is 3.92, with a standard deviation of 0.954. Generation Z's range of values is from 4 to 5, and the mean is 4.25, with a standard deviation of 0.463.
- b. Periodically check the profit/loss of the business. In the baby boomer generation, the range of values is from 3 to 5, with a mean of 4.00 and a standard deviation of 0.632. In Generation X, the range of values is from 4 to 5, and the mean is 4.43, with a standard deviation of 0.514. In Generation Y, the range of values is from 2 to 5, with a mean of 4.00 with a standard deviation of 0.707. In Generation Z, the range of values is from 1 to 4, and the mean is 4.13, with a standard deviation of 0.354.
- c. Setting aside business income for savings. In the baby boomer generation, the range of values is from 3 to 5, with a mean of 4.17 and a standard deviation of 0.753. In Generation X, the range of values is from 4 to 5, and the mean is 4.50, with a standard deviation of 0.519. In Generation Y, the range of values is from 2 to 5, with a mean of 4.00 with a standard deviation of 1.00. In Generation Z, the range of values is from 4 to 5, and the mean is 4.38, with a standard deviation of 0.518.
- d. Taking insurance to reduce future risks. In the baby boomer generation, the range of values is from 2 to 4, with a mean of 3.33 and a standard deviation of 0.816. In Generation X, the range of values is from 2 to 5, and the mean is 3.64, with a standard deviation of 1.216. In Generation Y, the range of values is from 2 to 5, and the mean is 2.92, with a standard deviation of 1.256. In Generation Z, the range of values is from 2 to 5, and the mean is 3.75, with a standard deviation of 0.886.
- e. Setting aside income for future investment. In the baby boomer generation, the score ranges from 4 to 5, with a mean of 4.17 and a standard deviation of 0.408. Generation X's score ranges from 4 to 5, with a mean of 4.43 and a standard deviation of 0.514. In Generation Y, the score ranges from 2 to 5, with a mean of 4.08 and a standard deviation of 0.760. Generation Z's score ranges from 4 to 5, with a mean of 4.13 and a standard deviation of 0.354.
- f. Thinking about the risks of taking on debt/credit before deciding. In the baby boomer generation, the range of values is from 2 to 5, with an average of 3.83 and a standard deviation of 0.983. In Generation X, the range of values is from 4 to 5; the highest value is 5, and the average is 4.36, with a standard deviation of 0.497. Generation Y's range of values is from 4 to 5; the average is 4.31, with a standard deviation of 0.480. In Generation Z, the range of values is from 2 to 5, and the average is 4.00, with a standard deviation of 0.926.

Table 1 presents the validity and reliability tests on 41 samples, which show that the research instrument used is valid, with a correlation value greater than 0.3 and a reliability coefficient (Cronbach Alpha) greater than 0.6. The test results also show that all questions for the financial literacy level variable (X) have a correlation value greater than 0.3. While the alpha coefficient is 0.621, this value is more significant than 0.6. Thus, the questions for the FL level variable (X) are valid and reliable for further testing.

Table 1. Validity and Reliability Test of Financial Literacy Level Variable (X)

Variable	Item Number	Validity		Alpha Coefficient
		Correlation (r)	Probability (p)	
X	X1	0.587	0.000	0.621
	X2	0.558	0.000	
	X3	0.533	0.000	
	X4	0.668	0.000	
	X5	0.488	0.002	
	X6	0.432	0.005	

Source: Data processed (2024)

Table 2 shows that all questions for the financial management capability variable (Y) have a correlation value greater than 0.3. While the alpha coefficient is 0.794, this value is more significant than 0.6. Thus, the questions for the financial management capability level variable (Y) are valid and reliable for further testing.

Table 2. Validity and Reliability Test of Financial Management Ability Variable (Y)

Variable	Item Number	Validity		Alpha Coefficient
		Correlation (r)	Probability (p)	
Y	Y1	0.819	0.000	0.794
	Y2	0.724	0.000	
	Y3	0.863	0.000	
	Y4	0.662	0.000	
	Y5	0.823	0.000	
	Y6	0.492	0.001	

Source: Data processed (2024)

The results of the test of differences in FL levels between generations using independent sample tests, both with Levene's test for equality of variance and t-test for equality of means, can be seen in Table 3 below:

Table 3. Difference Test Results

GEN	BB		X		Y		Z	
	Levene's test	t-test of means						
BB			0.934	0.699	0.568	0.701	0.845	0.133
X					0.400	0.338	0.748	0.128

Y		0.656	0.440
Z			

Source: Data processed (2024)

From Table 3, it appears that the significance value of the difference test between the baby boomers and Generation X, between baby boomers and Y, between baby boomers and Z, between X and Y, between X and Z, and between Y and Z using Levene's test for equality of variance has a significance value of all more than 0.05 (5%), this means that the hypothesis is rejected, so it can be concluded that there is no difference in literacy levels between generations when viewed from the variance. However, when viewed from the results of the difference test using the t-test for equality of means, it appears that the significance value of the difference test between the baby boomers and generation X, between baby boomers and Y, between baby boomers and Z, between X and Y, between X and Z has a significance value all greater than 0.05 (5%), this means that the hypothesis is rejected. Only between Y and Z has a significance value smaller than 0.05 (5%), which means the thesis is accepted. So there is no difference between baby boomers and Generation X, baby boomers and Y, baby boomers and Z, X and Y, X and Z, or Y and Z.

The results of the test of differences in financial management abilities between generations using independent sample tests, both with Levene's test for equality of variance and t-test for equality of means, can be seen in Table 4:

Table 4. Difference Test Results

GEN	BB		X		Y		Z	
	Levene's test	t-test of means						
BB			0.527	0.131	0.383	0.738	0.685	0.543
X					0.419	0.059	0.968	0.403
Y							0.537	0.367
Z								

Source: Data processed (2024)

From Table 4, it appears that the significant value of the difference test regarding the ability to manage finances between the baby boomers and Generation X, between baby boomers and Y, between baby boomers and Z, between X and Y, between X and Z and between Y and Z using Levene's test for equality of variance has a significance value of all more than 0.05 (5%), this means that the hypothesis is rejected, so it can be concluded that there is no difference in the ability to manage finances between generations when viewed from the variance. Likewise, when viewed from the results of the difference test using the t-test for equality of means, it appears that the significance value of the difference test between the baby boomers and generation X, between baby boomers and Y, between baby boomers and Z, between X and Y, between X and Z and between Y and Z have a significance value of all greater than 0.05 (5%) which means that the hypothesis is rejected. So it can be concluded that there is no difference in the ability to manage finances between the baby boomers and Generation X, between baby boomers and Y, between baby boomers and Z, between X and Y, between X and Z, and between generations Y and Z.

A simple linear regression analysis was used to determine the effect of literacy level (X) on financial management ability (Y). The results of the simple linear regression analysis can be seen in Table 5 :

Table 5. Simple Regression Analysis Results

Variable	Unstandardize d Coefficients (B)	T count	Sig.	Information
(Constant)	11.548			
Financial Literacy Level (X)	0.543	2.521	0.016	Significant
R	= 0.374			
R Square	= 0.140			
Sign. F	= 0.016			
σ	= 0.05			

The dependent variable in this regression is Financial Management Ability (Y), while the independent variable is FL Level (X). The regression model based on the results of the analysis above is:

$$Y = 11.548 + 0.543X$$

The interpretation of this equation is:

1. $\beta_0 = 11.548$
This constant value shows that if there is no FL Level Variable (X=0), the ability to manage finances (Y) is 11.548. In other words, the ability to manage finances (Y) is 11.548 before or without the FL Level Variable.
2. $\beta_1 = 0.543$
The parameter value or regression coefficient β_1 shows that for every 1-fold increase in the FL Level variable (X), the ability to manage finances (Y) will increase by 0.543 times. In other words, for every increase in Financial Management Ability (Y), a FL Level variable of 0.543 is required.

The hypothesis is to be tested using simple regression analysis. The formulation of the hypothesis to be answered is "Does the Level of Financial Literacy (X) affect the Ability to Manage Finances (Y)." The significance result produced is 0.016; this value is smaller than 0.05 (5%); the hypothesis is accepted, so it can be concluded that the level of FL affects the ability to manage finances. The R² value is 0.140, which means that the magnitude of the influence of financial literacy on the ability to manage finances is 14%, and the remaining 86% that the ability to manage finances is influenced by other factors besides the level of FL.

Table 6. Recapitulation of Research Results

	Hypothesis	Information
H1	There are differences in the level of FL in each generation.	Rejected
H2	There are differences in the ability to manage finances in each generation.	Rejected
H3	Each generation's FL level influences their ability to manage finances.	Accepted

Discussion

The first finding of the research results shows that there is no difference in FL levels between the Baby Boomer Generation and Generation X, between the Baby Boomer Generation and Generation Y, between the Baby Boomer Generation and Generation Z, between X and Y, between X and Z, and between Y and Z. This is because first, both the baby boomers, X, Y and Z generations have the same access to financial education so that they have comparable levels of literacy, second, all generations can adapt to technology so that there is no gap in mastering financial information. Third, the knowledge about finance learned by each generation is the same, so the literacy level between generations will be the same. Amonhaemanon and Vora-Sitta (2020) found on the contrary that FL of each generation group is different. Gen Y has a higher average FL score than Gen X and Gen B.

The second finding of the research results revealed that there is no difference in the ability to manage finances between the baby boomer generation and Generation X, between the baby boomer generation and Generation Y, between the baby boomer generation and Generation Z, between Generation X and Generation Y, between Generation X and Generation Z, and between Generation Y and Generation Z. This is because first, all generations, be it baby boomers, X, Y and Z, are under the same economic policy and similar economic stability so that they will have almost the same financial management skills. Second, all generations get almost the same financial education, which can lead to the same ability to manage finances; third, all generations have the exact basic financial needs, such as paying debts, planning a budget, and saving for the future, so that their financial management skills are the same. Carlin et al. (2019) revealed that the financial management skills of the millennial generation are better than the older generation. Luther et al. (2018) found that Baby Boomers are more likely to use financial planning services for financial management, followed by Generation X and Millennials.

The latest research findings prove that the level of FL influences the ability to manage finances. This result is consistent with Lusardi and Mitchell (2014), who stated that the level of FL directly impacts the ability to make financial decisions. The higher the level of financial literacy, the more capable a person is in managing their finances effectively. Navickas et al. (2014) revealed that financial literacy has a positive impact on personal financial management for Generation Z. Ameliawati and Setiyani (2018) also proved a positive relationship between financial literacy and financial management behaviour.

Conclusion

This study aims to investigate the impact of literacy levels on the ability to manage the personal finances of small traders based on birth generation. The results of the study found that each generation's FL level (baby boomer, X, Y, and Z) is the same in terms of variance. Second, the level of FL between baby boomers and generation X, between baby boomers and Y, between baby boomers and Z, between X and Y, and between X and Z is the same but different between generations Y and Z when viewed in terms of its mean, third, the level of financial management ability of each generation is the same when viewed in terms of variance and mean, fourth, the level of FL of each generation affects its ability to manage its finances, fifth, the magnitude of the influence of the level of FL on the ability to manage finances is 14%, the remaining 86% that the ability to manage finances is influenced by factors other than the level of FL. Based on the limitations of this study, further research is needed by increasing the number of samples used in the study. Second, because the influence of other variables is 86%, adding other variables that influence the ability to manage finances, such as the experience variable, is recommended.

Conflict of interest

The authors hereby declare that no conflict of interest exists

References

- Abrahamson, P. (2016). End of an Era? China's One-Child Policy and its Unintended Consequences. *Asian Social Work and Policy Review*, 10(3), 326-338. <https://doi.org/10.1111/aswp.12101>
- Ameliawati, M., & Setiyani, R. (2018). The influence of financial attitude, financial socialization, and financial experience to financial management behavior with financial literacy as the mediation variable. *KnE Social Sciences*, 811-832. DOI 10.18502/kss.v3i10.3174
- Amonhaemanon, D., & Vora-Sitta, P. (2020). From financial literacy to financial capability: A preliminary study of difference generations in informal labor market. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(12), 355-363. doi:10.13106/jafeb.2020.vol7.no12.355
- Andarsari, P. R., & Ningtyas, M. N. (2019). The role of financial literacy on financial behavior. *Journal of accounting and business education*, 4(1), 24–33.
- Carlin, B., Olafsson, A., & Pagel, M. (2019). Generational differences in managing personal finances. In *AEA Papers and Proceedings* (Vol. 109, pp. 54-59). 2014 Broadway, Suite 305, Nashville, TN 37203: American Economic Association.
- Cwynar, A. (2020). Financial literacy, behavior and well-being of millennials in Poland compared to previous generations: The insights from three large-scale surveys. *Review of Economic Perspectives*, 20(3), 289–335. <https://doi.org/10.2478/revcep-2020-0015>

- Endri, E., Dermawan, D., Abidin, Z., Riyanto, S. (2019). Effect of Financial Performance on Stock Return: Evidence from the Food and Beverages Sector. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 9(10), 335-350.
- Endri, E., Syafarudin, A., Santoso, S., Imaningsih, E. S., Suharti, T., & Rinda, R. T. (2020). Consumption behavior patterns of generations Y Halal products in Indonesia. *Academy of Entrepreneurship Journal*, 26(2), 1-10.
- Gutter, M. S., Wang, L., & Way, W. (2008). Financial management practices of college students from states with varying financial education mandates. *National Endowment for Financial Education*, 1–20.
- Huston, S. J. (2010). Measuring financial literacy. *Journal of Consumer Affairs*, 44(2), 296-316. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-6606.2010.01170.x>
- Karakurum-Ozdemir, K., Kokkizil, M., & Uysal, G. (2019). Financial literacy in developing countries. *Social Indicators Research*, 143, 325-353. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-018-1952-x>
- Lusardi, A., & Mitchell, O. S. (2014). The economic importance of financial literacy: Theory and evidence. *American Economic Journal: Journal of Economic Literature*, 52(1), 5-44.
- Luther, R., Coleman, L. J., Kelkar, M., & Foudray, G. (2018). Generational differences in perceptions of financial planners. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 23(2), 112-127. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41264-018-0046-9>
- Mancebón, M. J., Ximénez-de-Embún, D. P., Mediavilla, M., & Gómez-Sancho, J. M. (2019). Factors that influence the financial literacy of young Spanish consumers. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 43(2), 227-235.
- Mawad, J. L., Athari, S. A., Khalife, D., & Mawad, N. (2022). Examining the impact of financial literacy, financial self-control, and demographic determinants on individual financial performance and behavior: An insight from the Lebanese Crisis Period. *Sustainability*, 14(22), 15129. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142215129>
- Navickas, M., Gudaitis, T., & Krajnakova, E. (2014). Influence of financial literacy on management of personal finances in a young household. *Business: theory and practice*, 15(1), 32-40. <https://doi.org/10.3846/btp.2014.04>
- Onyango, A. A. (2021). Determinants of personal financial management decisions: a comparison of self-employed generation X and generation Y in Embakasi East Constituency of Nairobi, Kenya. *African Journal of Emerging Issues*, 3(3), 83-104. Retrieved from <https://ajoeijournals.org/sys/index.php/ajoei/article/view/183>
- Patrisia, D., Abror, A., Dastgir, S., & Rahayu, R. (2023). Generation Z's financial behavior: The role of Islamic financial literacy. *ISRA International Journal of Islamic Finance*, 15(2), 20–37. <https://doi.org/10.55188/ijif.v15i2.540>

- Pokharel, J., & Maharjan, I. (2024). Financial Behavior of Generation Z and Millennials. *Journal of Emerging Management Studies, 1*(2), 148–170. <https://doi.org/10.3126/jems.v1i2.71522>
- Potrich, A. C. G., Matheis, T. K., & Vieira, K. M. (2024). Gender Differences in Financial Literacy Between and Within Generations. *Journal of Financial Counseling and Planning, 35*(3), 381-399. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1891/JFCP-2023-0058>
- Rahmadani, Y., Sulistyowati, A., Wahyu, C. I., & Yunita, T. (2023). The Effect of Financial Literacy and Financial Attitude on Financial Management Behavior in Generation Z in Bekasi Regency. *IJESM Indonesian Journal of Economics and Strategic Management, 1*(4), 474-483.
- Susanto, K.P., Mandagie, W.C., Endri, E., & Wiwaha, A. (2025). Financial literacy, technological progress, financial attitudes and investment decisions of Gen Z Indonesian investors. *Investment Management and Financial Innovations, 22*(1), 25-34. [https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi.22\(1\).2025.03](https://doi.org/10.21511/imfi.22(1).2025.03)
- Widyastuti, M., Indrawati, L., & Paula, P. (2022). Level of financial literacy reviewed various factors on economic students. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR), 6*(2), 1278-1285.
- Wijaya, H. R., Hati, S. R. H., Ekaputra, I. A., & Kassim, S. (2024). The impact of religiosity and financial literacy on financial management behavior and well-being among Indonesian Muslims. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications, 11*(1), 1-13.
- Xie, X., Osińska, M., & Szczepaniak, M. (2023). Do young generations save for retirement? Ensuring financial security of Gen Z and Gen Y. *Journal of Policy Modeling, 45*(3), 644-668. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpolmod.2023.05.003>
- Yanti, F., & Endri, E. (2024). Financial Behavior, Overconfidence, Risk Perception and Investment Decisions: The Mediating Role of Financial Literacy. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues, 14*(5), 289–298. <https://doi.org/10.32479/ijefi.16811>